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Silver(I) dithiocarbamate on modified magnetic cellulose Synthesis, density functional theory study and application

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Abstract

A magnetically retrievable catalytic system involving Ag(I) dithiocarbamate supported on functionalized cellulose was prepared. The structure of this hybrid nano-composite was characterized by various techniques. In addition, to describe the metal-ligand interactions present in the nano-composite, covalent and electrostatic interactions, density functional theory model and quantum theory of atoms in molecule method were employed. The resultant nano-composite exhibits remarkable catalytic efficacy in the synthesis of 2-amino-6-(2-oxo-2H-chromen-3-yl)-4-phenylnicotinonitriles from the reaction of 3-acetylcoumarin, aromatic aldehydes, and malononitrile. Its recoverability and reusability for this catalyst was examined in several runs, which showed no appreciable loss after five runs. The facile accessibility to the starting materials, and conducting the reactions in the eco-friendly and cost-effective conditions are the other merits of such new catalyst. Ambient reaction conditions, wide substrate scope, and facile accessibility to the starting materials, are some of the other outstanding features of this protocol that make it economic and sustainable.

Keywords: Magnetic biomaterial, Chromene-linked nicotinonitrile, Metal-ligand interactions